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Review Article

**INDOLES AS THERAPEUTICS OF INTEREST IN MEDICINAL
CHEMISTRY**C. Buvana^{1*}, R. Suresh¹, Y. Haribabu², P. K. Manna¹^{1*,2}Department of Pharmaceutical chemistry, Grace College of Pharmacy, Palakkad, Kerala.¹Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, India**Abstract:**

Indole is a valuable compound which has become prominent in medicinal chemistry because of its various biological activities. Indole ring is present in various marine or terrestrial natural compounds, which have useful biological properties. In last few years it was reported that indole, its bioisosters and derivatives had antimicrobial activity against gram-negative, gram-positive bacteria and yeast candida albicans antimicrobial activity. A large number of efforts were made to synthesize different heterocyclic compounds and their derivatives in the past decade and were found to possess promising antitumor, anticonvulsant, antimicrobial anti-tubercular and anti-diabetic activities. Although indole moiety is very small but is fascinated by scientists because of the diverse biological activities by not only indole but its various substituted derivatives as well. This review is focused on the indole and its derivatives that are now in development. This review brings about an overview of novel drug molecules of indole and also urges to synthesize more moieties for better enhanced biological activity.

Keywords: Indole, Antimalarial, Anticancer, Antimicrobial, Antihypertensive**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION: [1]

The name *indoleis* portmanteau of the words *indigo* and *oleum*. Indole is an aromatic heterocyclic organic compound. It has a bicyclic structure, consisting of a benzene ring and a pyrrole nucleus are fused in 2, 3 positions of the pyrrole ring. Indole is non-basic nitrogenous compound. 1-3 Indole chemistry began to develop with the study of the dye indigo. The word Indole is coined from the word India, a blue dye imported from India known as Indigo. Indigo can be converted to isatin and then to oxindole. 4-5 In 1866, Adolf von Baeyer reduced oxindole to indole[1] by using zinc dust. In 1869; he proposed a formula for indole.

Fig. 1: Bayer's structure of indole

Indole derivatives occur widely in natural products, plants, animals and marine organisms.¹⁶ Many

natural products contains indole nucleus like heteroauxin[2], tryptophan [3], hypaphorine[4], bufotenin[5] and gramine[6] [Fig. 1]. Various plants contains indole as a core component like Robiniapseudacacia, Jasmine, citrus fruits and orange blossoms. Serotonin [7] contains indole nucleus and biochemically derived from tryptophan, is a neurotransmitter and is found in all bilateral animals. Melatonin [8], is a hormone found in animals, plants, and microbes and meant for the control of diurnal rhythm of physiological functions. An indole alkaloid like Ajmaline [9], Reserpine [10] is used to treat high blood pressure and severe agitation in patients with mental disorders. Vinblastine is anticancer agent being recognized tubulin polymerization inhibitor and used in the treatment of acute lymphoblastic leukemia and against both Hodgkins and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. Sumatriptan [11] and ondansetron [12] are highly selective medicines for the treatment of migraine and suppression of nausea, vomiting caused by cancer chemotherapy respectively. Indomethacin [13] is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug commonly used to reduce fever, pain, stiffness and swelling by inhibiting production of prostaglandin [2-12].

Fig. 2: Structures of indole containing natural products and drugs

Indole represents one of the most important structural motifs in drug discovery, and it is described as one of the "privileged scaffolds". Indole derivatives and its

pharmacological significance provides tremendous opportunities to discover novel drugs with different modes of action.

Fig. 3: Pharmacological significance of indole

AUTHOR	SYNTHESISED COMPOUNDS	THERAPEUTIC INDICATION
<p>Antimicrobial activity Heba m. abo-salem et al [13]</p>		Antimicrobial activity
<p>Adel hamed mandour et.al[14]</p>		Antimicrobial activity
<p>Mari'a C. et al[15]</p>		Antimicrobial activity
<p>Faritha A et al [16]</p>		Antimicrobial activity

<p>Jaiprakash S. Biradar et al., [17]</p>	<p>(a-i)</p>	<p>Antimicrobial agents.</p>
<p>Saundane Anand R et.al., [18]</p>		<p>Antimicrobial Activity</p>
<p>Asmaa S et.al[19]</p>		<p>Antimicrobial Activity</p>
<p>Pandeya S.N. et.al[20]</p>		<p>Anti microbial agent</p>
<p>SüreyyaÖlgena,Nurt en Altanlarb et. al. [21]</p>	<p>R= 4-Cl-phenyl, 4-F-phenyl, 2,4-Cl-phenyl</p>	<p>Antimicrobial, antifungal and anti-HBV activities</p>
<p>Kumar et al[22]</p>		<p>Antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activit</p>
<p><u>Antiinflammatory activity</u> Reddy et al[23]</p>		<p>Anti-inflammatoryactivity</p>

Rani et al[24]		Anti-inflammatory
Minakshi Shroff et al[25]		Anti-inflammatory
SMuralikrishna et al[26]		Anti-inflammatory activity
El-Sayed <i>et al.</i> [27]		Cyclooxygenase [COX] inhibition
Mohammad mumtaz alam et al., [28]		Anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activity
Sally et al [29]		Antitumor and Anti-inflammatory

Amir et.al[30]		Anti-inflammatory agents
Radwanet.al[31]		Analgesic activity
Kumar et al[32]		Anti-inflammatory activity
Manaet al[33]		Anti-inflammatory activity
<u>Anticonvulsant & anti depressant activity</u> Mohamed Jawed Ahsan, et al[34]		Anticonvulsant activity
Pravin O patil et al[35]		Antidepressant and anticonvulsant
Slasi,A et. al[36]		Treatment of CNS disease

Siddiquet al[37]		Anticonvulsant
Abele et al. [38]		Antidepressant activity
Anti-cancer activity		
Abdou O. et al[39]		Anticancer Agents
Asmafahmy et al[40]		Anti tumour&anti microbial activity
Liou et al[41]		Anticancer agents
Sigman et al[42]		Anticancer activity against MCF-7 cells
Popp and Pajouhesh et al[43]		Lymphoid leukaemia

Doris Kaufmann et al[44]		Treatment of breast cancer
Fan Zhang et al[45]	<p>$R^1 = 3, 4,$</p>	Anti-tumor activity
Ulrich Jacquemard et al[46]		CDK inhibitors and cytotoxic agents
Ekhl Nassar et al[47]		Antitumor and antimicrobial activity
Huasheng Ding et al[48]	<p>$R_1 = H, OCH_3$ $R_2 = H, CH_3$</p>	Potent inhibitors for AKT-m TOR signaling pathway kinases
Magdy A H Zahran et al[49]	<p>$R = \text{Allyl, Benzyl}$ $Ar = C_6H_5, 4-MeC_6H_4$ $Ar' = C_6H_5, 3NO_2, 4PhC_6H_4$</p>	Antitumor activity
Abdel-Rahman Farghaly et al[50]		Antitumor activity

Ahmed Kamal et al[51]	<p> $R_1 = \text{H, 5Cl, 5Br, 5NO}_2$ $R_2 = \text{H, F}$ $R_3 = \text{H, CH}_3$ </p>	Anticancer activities
Yu-Shan Wu et al[52]	<p>$R = \text{I, CH}_3, \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$</p>	Anticancer activities
Palwinder Singh et al[53]	<p> $R_1 = \text{H, butene, butyne, C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{ethane, C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3, \text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COCH}_3$ </p>	Anticancer activities
Radulovicet al[54]		Anticancer agents.
Shchekotikhinet al[55]		Anticancer agents.
Guan et al[56]		Anticancer agents.
Jun-Rong Jiang et al[57]		Anticancer activity

Wen-Tai Li <i>et al</i> [58]		Orally Anticancer activity
<u>ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTY</u> Zeynepates-alagoz <i>et al</i> [59]		Antioxidant property
Enienet <i>al</i> [60]		Antioxidant property
Talazet <i>al</i> [61]		Antioxidant property
<u>ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY</u> Selvamet <i>al</i> [62]		Antiviral activity
Dun Wang <i>et al</i> [63]		Antiviral activity
Abele <i>et al.</i> [64]		Antiviral activity

There are also an amazing number of indole containing drugs in the market.

INDOLE-CONTAINING DRUGS[65]

NAME OF THE DRUG	STRUCTURE	COMPANY NAME	BRAND NAME	THERAPEUTIC APPLICATION
1. Triptans a) Sumatriptan		Glaxo smithkline	Imitrex	Antimigraine
b) Naratriptan		Glaxosmithkline	Naramig	Antimigraine
c) Rizatriptan		Merck	Maxalt	Antimigraine
d) Amlotriptan			Axert	Antimigraine
e) Frovatriptan		Glaxosmithkline	Frova	Antimigraine
f) Eletriptan		Pfizer	Relpax	Antimigraine
g) Zolmitriptan		Glaxosmithkline	Zomig	Antimigraine

2. a) Fluvastatin		Merck	Lescol, Lescol XL	Treatment of Hypercholesterolemia & lipoproteinemia
b) Lovastatin		Novartis	Mevacor, Altoprev, Altacor	Treatment of Hypercholesterolemia & lipoproteinemia
c) Simvastatin		Novartis	Zocor, FloLipid	Treatment of Hypercholesterolemia & lipoproteinemia
d) Atrovastatin		Pfizer	Lipitor	Treatment of Hypercholesterolemia & lipoproteinemia
3. a) Tadalafil		Apollo Life Sciences Pvt Ltd	Adcirca, Cialis	Used to treat erectile dysfunction or pulmonary arterial hypertension;
B) Sildenafil		Pfizer	Revatio, Viagra	used to treat erectile dysfunction and pulmonary arterial hypertension
c) Vardenafil		A.D.Pharmaceuticals	Levitra.	used for treating erectile dysfunction

4. a) Ondansetron		Glaxosmithkline	Zofran	Antiemetic caused by cancer chemotherapy, radiation therapy, or surgery
b) Alosetron		Glaxosmithkline	Lotronex	Antiemetic
c) Romosetron		AstellasPharma	Nozia	Antiemetic
d) Dolasetron		Sanofi- Aventis	Anzemet	Antiemetic
e) Tropisetron		Astamedica	Novoban	Antiemetic
5. Tegaserod		Novartis	Zelmac	Totreat chronic idiopathic constipation
6. Zafirlukast		Astra Zeneca	Accolate	used for the chronic treatment of asthma
7. Sertindole		Lundbeck	Compazine	antipsychotics,

8. Delavirdine		Pfizer	Rescriptor	Highly active antiretroviral therapy [HAART] for the treatment of [HIV] type 1
9. Daptomycin		Lilly/cubist	Cubicin	antibiotic
10. Eptifibatid		COR Therapeutics/ schering-plough	Integrillin	antiplatelet drug

INDOLINE CONTAINING DRUG

NAME OF THE DRUG	STRUCTURE	COMPANY NAME	BRAND NAME	THERAPEUTIC APPLICATION
Sildenafil		Watson	Rapaflo	Treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia

OXYINDOLE CONTAINING DRUG

NAME OF THE DRUG	STRUCTURE	COMPANY NAME	BRAND NAME	THERAPEUTIC APPLICATION
a) Ziprasidone		Pfizer	Geodon	Antipsychotic

b) <u>Ropinirole</u>		<u>Glaxosmithkline</u>	<u>Requip</u>	Treatment of Parkinson's disease
c) <u>Sunitinib</u>		<u>Pfizer</u>	<u>Sutent</u>	Treatment of renal cell carcinoma

CONCLUSION:

The present review summarizes all pharmacological aspects of the indole based molecules. A large number of drug molecules possessing indole nucleus, whether from natural origin or synthesized in laboratory, have been reported for the treatment of various disease conditions. Many of these molecules have been approved by FDA and are being currently utilized in drug therapies. We hope that in this review provides information regarding how the indole nucleus can be utilized by a medicinal chemist for the design and development of clinically viable molecules.

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